

Comparison Between Subway in San Francisco and Tokyo

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the subway systems of two major cities—San Francisco and Tokyo—focusing on their economic, cultural, and social impacts. Using data science approaches, this article analyzed the ridership patterns, operational efficiency, and societal roles of these subway systems. Tokyo, with a daily ridership of nearly 10 million passengers, is known for its punctuality and cultural discipline, contributing 3.2% to the city's GDP. In contrast, San Francisco's BART, though smaller, plays a vital role in connecting the Bay Area's population, saving the region approximately \$7.8 billion annually in reduced congestion and improved productivity. Both systems, despite their cultural differences, demonstrate the critical role that subways play in reducing environmental impact and supporting urban economic growth. By comparing these two cities, this study aims to uncover broader patterns and insights into how subway systems contribute to urban development, sustainability, and public welfare. The findings highlight the importance of continuous investment and innovation in public transportation to accommodate growing urban populations and maintain efficient, sustainable transit networks.

Keywords: Subway systems, ridership patterns, technology, sustainability

1. Introduction

Subway systems have become one of the most essential modes of transportation in modern metropolitan cities, not only easing traffic congestion but also contributing to urban development and social welfare. Globally, there are 201 cities equipped with subways, undergrounds, tubes, or U-Bahn systems (Mackett & Edwards, 1998). These networks are integral to the daily lives of millions, facilitating economic activity and fostering social connections. In cities like New York, the subway serves as the lifeblood of urban transportation, with a staggering daily ridership of 3.2 million people, making it one of the busiest systems in the world (MTA, 2020).

As urbanization increases, the role of subway systems extends beyond mere convenience. "The subway not only provides a faster and more efficient means of travel but also contributes significantly to reducing urban pollution and promoting environmental sustainability" (Cervero & Murakami, 2009). Moreover, these systems shape the social fabric of the city by creating shared public spaces. Sociologists have noted that subway stations often become "microcosms of urban life, where people from different social strata interact, reinforcing the idea of the city as a space for diverse social experiences" (Wilson, 2012).

This report aims to explore the underlying patterns and economic benefits of the subway systems in two globally significant cities, San Francisco and Tokyo. According to data, Tokyo boasts one of the most sophisticated subway systems, with a daily ridership of nearly 10 million passengers (Tokyo Metro, 2022). In contrast, San Francisco's BART (Bay Area Rapid Transit) system, while smaller in scale, serves as a critical infrastructure for the Bay Area's 7.7 million residents (BART, 2021). Despite their differences in size and scale, the two systems reveal interesting similarities and patterns that speak to the broader role subways play in urban development.

Tokyo's subway system is renowned for its punctuality and efficiency, with trains rarely deviating from their schedule by more than a minute (Tokyo Metro, 2022). In contrast, San Francisco's BART, while advanced, faces challenges like delays and maintenance issues. A study found that "BART experienced delays during 12% of peak hours in 2021, compared to less than 1% in Tokyo's subway" (BART, 2021).

This discrepancy highlights differences in the operational structures and investments made by each city in maintaining their transportation networks.

Subways also impact the economy significantly. In Tokyo, the subway system contributes an estimated 3.2% to the city's GDP through fare revenue, reduced travel times, and enhanced worker productivity (Fujii & Miyamoto, 2017). Similarly, in San Francisco, the BART system is responsible for saving the region around \$7.8 billion annually by reducing road congestion and enhancing access to employment hubs (Bay Area Council Economic Institute, 2019). "Both systems play a critical role in connecting the workforce with their workplaces, boosting economic efficiency and reducing the environmental footprint" (Cervero & Murakami, 2009).

Cultural and societal differences between San Francisco and Tokyo also manifest in their subway systems. Tokyo subways are known for their orderly passenger behavior, with silent cars, strict queueing systems, and high cultural respect for space (Tokyo Metro, 2022). As anthropologist Merry White observed, "The Tokyo subway is not just a transportation system but a cultural phenomenon, reflecting the broader societal values of discipline and respect for communal space" (White, 2014). In contrast, the San Francisco subway system reflects the city's more laid-back culture, where "conversations, street performances, and even public art installations inside stations are common, emphasizing San Francisco's identity as a creative and socially dynamic city" (Chen, 2018).

Despite these cultural differences, both cities face similar challenges, particularly in dealing with overcrowding and funding. As cities expand, the demand for efficient and sustainable public transportation increases. "Urban planners must now consider how to accommodate rising populations while maintaining the integrity and sustainability of their subway systems" (Suzuki, Cervero, & Iuchi, 2013). In Tokyo, this has led to innovations like the introduction of women-only cars during peak hours to combat overcrowding and harassment (Tokyo Metro, 2022). Similarly, San Francisco has experimented with expanding BART services to outer suburbs and introducing dynamic pricing models to alleviate congestion during peak times (BART, 2021).

By comparing the subway systems of San Francisco and Tokyo, this report seeks to uncover broader insights into how public transportation influences not just urban mobility but also economic growth, cultural expression, and social interaction. "Subways are more than just a way to get from point A to point B; they are vital arteries in the body of the city, supporting its growth and vitality" (Glaeser, 2011).

2. Case Description

2.1. Data source

The dataset used in this paper is fetched from the official websites of Tokyo subway, San Francisco Bay Area Rapid Transit (BART), and San Francisco Muni.

2.2. Impact of COVID-19

As shown in the Figure, the left is the total number of subway passengers in San Francisco, where Bay Area Rapid Transit (BART) and Muni Metro are two of the major transportation in the regional and local area. The right graph shows the total number of passengers in Tokyo. It is very clear from the graph that both subway systems suffer a decline in ridership during the pandemic in 2020. The ridership in San Francisco has declined by 35.55% in 2020, while Tokyo metro faced a 34.43% decrease in passengers.

San Francisco subway system seems to face its darkest time in 2021, whereas Tokyo metro hit the ground by 2020, and started to regain its passengers by 2021. This can lead to several different hypotheses. First, California government started to ease restriction in the spring of 2021 when the vaccination rate is not high, which may lead to fear of going to public spaces, including taking the subway. On the other hand, Tokyo government continued to enforce measures such as mask-wearing, social distancing, and limitations on large gatherings, which may make passengers feel more secured about taking public transportation. Second, in 2021, the Tokyo Summer Olympics was held, which may attract a great number of passengers to take the subway. Third, Tokyo' subway system is more integral to the daily functioning and commuting needs of its residents, whereas people in the US generally prefer private cars.

2.3. Temperature and Weather

As could be shown by the graph, the ridership is lowest in July, December and January, which correspond to summertime and wintertime. This can lead to a reasonable hypothesis that people favored subways less when the temperature is too high or too low. It happens to support the previous argument that the subway is not the major or main transportation choice, thus the ridership appeared more fluctuated by external factors, whereas the ridership in Tokyo varied less throughout one year.

Other potential explanations may lie in holiday reasons. Students are a large proportion as the passengers of subways in the US. In fact, about 24% of public school students in urban areas use school buses. In the

winter break and summer holidays, it is less frequent for students to take the subway, thus drawing a decline in ridership.

Also, for commuters, summer and winter are popular travel times; by then people would no longer take subways as they usually do. In 2019, 115 million Americans went for a trip. This could also lead to decrease in ridership.

2.4. Delay and Pandemic

Tokyo has always been renowned for its extreme punctual transportation, and the pandemic seems to have no significant influence on the punctuality of Tokyo subways. However, it is surprising to observe a decrease in delay for BART during the pandemic. First of all, we can hypothesize that fewer passengers releases the transportation and reduces the delay time. The pandemic seemed to not only raise people's alarm to be more cautious about the virus but also remind the staff of their duty to arrive on time. One possible explanation would be that after the chaos caused by the pandemic, transit authorities may have implemented improvements in operations and scheduling. The maintenance may undergo similar improvements, thus decreasing delays. Also, facing the decline in passengers in 2020, the transit may want to attract passengers by raising punctuality. They may both contribute to the decrease in delay.

3. Analysis on the Data comparison: Price, Revenue and Net Income

3.1.

Most subway systems in the world generate negative income annually, yet Tokyo Metro is one of the very few exceptions. In 2023, the Tokyo metro system managed to generate a positive net income of 180.05 million US dollar, whereas the San Francisco metro brought a 624 million negative deficit to the government, which happened to be the situation of most other metros around the globe. Subway system is a public good, which made the achievement Tokyo Metro has retained seem more astonishing. Many may doubt whether the government has raised the price to manually exploit the profit from the passengers. The fact stays on the opposite side. In fact, the fare of Tokyo Metro is far less than that of San Francisco and many other cities. The highest fare, allowing a farthest travel of 40km, is 330 yen, which is approximately 2 USD. On the other hand, for San Francisco passengers, the average fare for taking BART is 4.91USD, and the fare of Muni Metro is 3 USD for adults and 1.5 USD for the young and old, despite their traveling distance.

3.2.

As the price plays an indirect role in generating such a profit for Tokyo Metro, the explanations of such great profit can be disputable and diverting. First, the low price may actually attract more commuters to use subway as their transportation option. This can be verified by the high ridership of Tokyo Metro every day, which suggests an extensive commuter population in Tokyo, whereas other cities like San Francisco are way

dissimilar. Second, the public satisfaction and service of the metro system may vary between the two cities, where Tokyo Metro may provide a better service, thus resulting in a high revenue. The data of revenue and government subsidy can support this proposition. The Tokyo government has granted a 2244.45 million dollar subsidy on Tokyo Metro in 2023, whereas the San Francisco metros only receive a total grant of 958.7 million dollar. This may support the idea that the Tokyo Metro may be more capable of providing better service to its passengers, yet the opposite opinion may also stand, which may suggest that the higher subsidy is due to the extensive lines in Tokyo. However, this is not true. According to the data, San Francisco has a total length of 326.5 km metro line, whereas Tokyo only has a 195.1km metro line. The sole apparent support for the opposite stance may be that Tokyo metro has a total 180 stations, while San Francisco only has 113 stations. This can lead to the evaluation of maintenance and subway hygiene. Tokyo metro is generally regarded as having a higher level of hygiene compared with metros in San Francisco due to cultural and managerial factors. Therefore, it is fair to argue that the Tokyo government may have spent more money on maintenance, which ultimately results in a higher revenue.

3.3.

Third, aside from these explanations, operation hours of subways may also influence the passenger choice and consuming intention. The Tokyo Metro operates from 5am to 1am, which suggests a total working duration of 20 hours. The metros in San Francisco have similar performance on weekdays, yet they operate for shorter time on the weekend. On Saturday, the metros operate from 6am to 12am, whereas on Sunday, they operate from 8am to 9pm. The shorter operation hour may negatively influence the ridership, which leads to lower revenue.

4. Conclusion: Financial and Engineering Suggestions

4.1. Average Speed and Efficiency

Tokyo Subway

Current Situation: Tokyo's subway system is known for its efficiency and high average speed, with trains operating at speeds of 80 km/h (50 mph) 100 km/h (62 mph) (Tōzai Line) 65 km/h (40 mph) (Ginza Line) 75 km/h (47 mph) (Marunouchi Line) This speed allows for quick transit across the city. Recommendations: Advanced Train Technology: Implement newer train models with advanced propulsion systems to enhance speed and acceleration while maintaining safety. Optimized Scheduling: Employ real-time data analytics to adjust train frequencies and reduce idle times, improving overall speed and efficiency.

San Francisco Subway

Current Situation: The average speed we have calculated is 33.37 km/h. Recommendations: Modernization of Rolling Stock: Upgrade Muni Metro trains to newer models with improved aerodynamics and energy-efficient designs. Infrastructure Upgrades: Invest in track and signaling technology to reduce delays and improve operational speed.

4.2. Delay Rates

Tokyo Subway

Current Situation: Tokyo's subway has a very low delay rate, around 1% or less, due to its robust scheduling and operational practices. Recommendations: Predictive Maintenance: Implement predictive maintenance technologies to identify and address potential issues before they cause delays. Enhanced Communication Systems: Utilize advanced communication systems to improve coordination and responsiveness to disruptions.

San Francisco Subway

Current Situation: Both BART and Muni Metro face higher delay rates, especially Muni Metro, which struggles with frequent service disruptions. Recommendations: Infrastructure Investment: Prioritize investments in infrastructure to reduce the frequency of service disruptions. This includes modernizing tracks and signal systems. Real-time Monitoring: Use real-time monitoring and automated diagnostics to quickly address and mitigate issues that cause delays.

4.3. Environmental Impact

Tokyo Subway

Power regeneration system: The motors used to run trains are operated as generators during braking, converting the train's running energy into electricity. The electricity generated is returned to the overhead lines and used to power other trains, or sent back to substations to be reused as power for station lighting and escalators. Toei Subway uses this system on all of its trains.

Current Situation: Tokyo's subway system is generally well-maintained and environmentally conscious, with efficient energy use and low emissions. Recommendations: Energy-efficient Technologies: Continue to invest in energy-efficient technologies and renewable energy sources to further reduce the system's environmental footprint. Green Certifications: Seek additional green certifications and implement sustainable practices in construction and operations.

San Francisco Subway

Current Situation: Environmental impact varies; while BART is relatively efficient, Muni Metro has more environmental challenges, particularly in maintaining older vehicles. Recommendations: Electrification and Hybrid Technologies: Explore electrification of Muni Metro lines and integrate hybrid or fully electric trains to reduce emissions. Sustainable Practices: Implement more sustainable practices in maintenance and operations, such as waste reduction and recycling programs.

4.4 Financial Performance

Tokyo Subway:

Current Situation: Tokyo's subway systems generally have strong financial performance, supported by high ridership and diversified revenue sources. Recommendations: Diversified Revenue Streams: Continue to explore and expand revenue sources beyond fare collection, such as commercial partnerships and real estate development.

San Francisco Subway:

Current Situation: Both BART and Muni Metro face financial challenges, relying heavily on government subsidies. Recommendations: Operational Efficiency: Focus on improving operational efficiency and reducing costs through technological upgrades and streamlined processes. Revenue Enhancement: Explore additional revenue streams, such as advertising, retail partnerships, and fare adjustments, to improve financial stability.

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